

Factors Affecting Financial Performance in Commercial Banks in Nepal

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Abstract

The financial performance is defined as the institutional economic status of the banking industry, which is undoubtedly considered a cornerstone of the Nepalese economy. This study examines the key factors that influence the financial performance of banking institutions in Nepal using a survey-based approach. Using a structured questionnaire, primary data were collected from a sample of 210 respondents, including bank employees, managers, and financial analysts across various commercial and development banks. The study looks at both internal and external determinants of financial performance, covering capital adequacy, asset quality, management efficiency, earnings, liquidity, and macroeconomic indicators. Descriptive statistics, correlation analysis, and multiple regression models were used to analyze the data and determine the strength and direction of relationships between these variables and financial performance, mainly measured through return on assets (ROA) and return on equity (ROE).

The findings show that capital adequacy, management efficiency, and asset quality have a significant positive effect on financial performance. Meanwhile, macroeconomic factors like inflation and GDP growth have a moderate influence. Liquidity, although important, shows an inconsistent relationship with performance depending on the bank's size and operational scale. The results highlight the importance of internal governance and risk management in improving performance metrics. The study adds to the limited empirical research on Nepal's banking sector by offering practical insights for policymakers, regulatory authorities, and banking professionals who aim to boost the sector's stability and profitability.

Keywords: *capital adequacy, commercial bank, financial performance, liquidity*